

Lost Possible Worlds: Toward a Narrative Approach to Computing Ethics

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Rather than an “a posteriori” approach to addressing the ethics of developing digital technologies, in which movement toward more ethical practice or deployment of technology occurs only after a certain technology negatively impacts certain populations, technological development must take an a priori approach in which multiple ethical ramifications of the technology are considered beforehand. This paper illuminates the power that narratives can provide to such an a priori approach, providing imaginative variations of potential technologies that those seated at the development table may consider. Using Paul Ricœur’s view of narratives as “ethical laboratories,” I argue that narratives, whether fictions or case studies, effectively provide good ethical deliberation at technology development tables through offering specific, contextual possibilities of how technology can affect or fail certain groups or populations. The narrative approach suggests a method of embedding ethical principles through viewing predictive narratives as imaginative variations of technologies that are distanced from such ethical principles. I dissect the short story “Burning Chrome” by William Gibson as a narrative that successfully predicted ethical and social discussions of digital networks and their impacts to prove the value of narratives in making a more informed developmental decision and serving as a crucial method for an a priori approach to technological development. I then discuss Gibson’s predictions in the context of the “Metaverse” to demonstrate how this narrative can serve as a crucial component of a priori deliberation in the development of this new networked environment.

Keywords: Computing Ethics, Technological Design and Development, Narrative, *A Priori*, Representation and Equitability

1 INTRODUCTION

In 1953, Ray Bradbury's *Fahrenheit 451* presented a dystopic society disturbingly immersed in a technological daze, the specifics of which might have seemed starkly unbelievable to readers of the time. Even to modern eyes, the idea of hyper-speed cars and rooms enclosed with immense TV walls becoming commonplace in society could be scorned as a vision that would never come to pass. However, the prescience of prediction in narratives, especially in genres such as science fiction, does not necessarily spring from perfect alignment with parallels to our digitized world. Ray Bradbury's imagination of his world's future may not have been perfect, but one imaginative thread in particular seems to resonate more than sixty years after the release of book: his concept of the seashell radio. The protagonist's wife Mildred is particularly enamored with these tiny devices that fit snugly into her ears, drawing her fully into whichever program she may be listening to while effectively cutting her off from the rest of the world and enabling her to ignore external stimuli. Again, this notion may have seemed ridiculous in the 1950s; a radio that is inserted directly into one's ears? Yet fast forward sixty-three years, and the modern reader can easily conceptualize such a device, likely by calling to mind an image of wireless Bluetooth headphones such as Apple's AirPods or its relatives. In 2019, Apple released the AirPods Pro, specifically designed with "Active Noise Cancellation" which can "cancel[...] external sounds before [the user] hear[s] them" (Apple Support). This capability of the AirPods to effectively plug the user in to certain content while actively blocking external "distractions" unrelated to the user's content popularized internet memes in which Airpod users are at imminent risk of perils such as traffic accidents based on the total immersion the device offers. In the eyes of Apple developers, this ability to isolate oneself in audio content with lessened external disruption is seen as an affordance of the device, one that would undoubtedly please users and turn an even larger profit for the company. Yet the narrative of *Fahrenheit 451* foretells a pitfall later detailed in the less serious format of internet jokes: total immersion through in-ear devices could cause users to notice less of their surroundings, leading to less authentic human connection and sometimes even dangerous scenarios. Did developers ever imagine such a consequence when formulating the affordances of AirPods, or would such a narrative have simply been dropped to the wayside at the developmental table in a race to release an appealing product?

How ironic that *Fahrenheit 451* details the burning of books, the dissolution of the great imaginations contained therein, when the narrative form has nearly boundless potential to inform how new technologies can be conceived, developed, and deployed in ways ethical and unethical. Jnanpith award-winning author Amitav Ghosh comments that imaginative literary genres which distance themselves from objective reality, such as "fantasy, horror, and science fiction," are often seen as removed from the realm of "serious fiction" (Ghosh 24). However, in a rapid, digitized society in which each successive technological development brings us further and further into new frontiers, a shortage of imagination allows the future to remain murky, shrouding the ethical impacts of the technologies we design. Put another way, we can no longer afford to distance ourselves from imaginations of how human-created technologies could potentially create dystopias, nor can we afford to distance such imaginative variations from the concept of "serious fiction." Technological developers must become practiced in envisioning the future before it arrives, considering a wealth of scenarios in which the artifacts they create inflict myriad impacts upon its user base rather than deploying artifacts with whatever affordances seem most feasible or lucrative and making alterations to technology products only after the impacts have been realized. This paper illuminates the strength of technological narratives to provide sound ethical deliberation during the developmental process on how certain technologies should be created and deployed through offering concrete possibilities on how such technologies may meet or fail to meet certain ethical principles.

1.1 Ricœur's Narrative Theory and Philosophical Frameworks

Using a foundation of Paul Ricœur's narrative theory, I will expound upon the philosophical justification for a narrative approach to computing ethics considerations through explaining its particular relevance to the developmental process. As digital technologies such as smartphones and expanded wireless communication networks continue to transform computing into a ubiquitous commodity, the manifold impacts of the specific coding and design choices of developers hold more sway. The question of extensive ethical deliberation grows in importance as the speed with which new technological developments reach and shape human societies also grows.

The Computing Ethics Narratives (CEN) project, an interdisciplinary approach to instruction in undergraduate computer science ethics founded through a collaboration between professors at Bowdoin and Colby colleges, two private liberal arts institutions for undergraduates located in Maine. The CEN project is similarly built upon Ricœur's philosophical foundation of the ability of narratives to explore ethical principles. A crucial tenet of this project is that "students need sustained assistance in developing an ethical sensibility to interpret the power and privilege they embody as tech creators through the design and production of new technologies" (Bullock et al 1021). While the CEN project specifically applies to developing ethical sensibility in undergraduate computer science students, its foundational principle of holistically considering the potentially vast consequences of coding or design decisions is easily extrapolated to the developmental process. The very existence of this project to remedy the problem of a lack of seamless ethics integration into computer science courses demonstrates the importance of narratives inspiring good ethical deliberation during the developmental process in the technology industry where these same undergraduates will likely end up.

Whether inspiring ethical deliberation in undergraduate classrooms or at the developmental table, narratives serve a unified function of inspiring critical thought on the specific consequences of certain decisions, rather than viewing computing function and capability in isolation from its direct results. Fernando Nascimento, a professor of Digital and Computational Studies at Bowdoin College, explains that "technology development processes tend to take into account internal aspects of technology such as durability, efficiency, material resilience, and response time, but rarely consider ethical concerns of how such technologies will affect the environments in which they will be used" (Nascimento 21). Further, as briefly considered in the discussion of Apple's AirPods above, certain market pressures could strongly incentivize developers to prioritize the internal workings or capabilities of a technology product, leaving external impacts on actors as a secondary consideration at best. A disproportionate, myopic focus on supposed affordances of a given artifact sidelines potential, situational negative impacts of these same affordances. The goal of a narrative-focused deliberative process at the developmental table would be to translocate the focus from internal capacities of a certain technology (what can be done) toward external impacts of specific decisions (what should be done).

In their capacity as exercises in imagination, narratives provide a stage for developers to envision concrete results of developmental choices, externalizing the meanings of the internal capabilities and operations of a given technology. For instance, the noise cancellation apparatus of Apple's AirPods Pro includes an option to toggle between Noise Cancellation mode and "Transparency" mode, in which the user can more easily perceive external stimuli, by either navigating several menus on the paired device or tapping the small sensors on the sides of the earbuds themselves. While this option somewhat addresses the ethical issue of total disconnection from one's surroundings, what becomes of those users whose fingers are not nimble enough to activate the small sensor, or those users whose lack of technical skills make navigation of on-screen menus difficult? Further, in the larger picture, do fine-grained alterations to the affordances of wear-able digital devices offset an overall trend toward disconnection that could arise as enablers for devices such as digital glasses potentially are developed? Paul Ricœur's view of narratives as "ethical laboratories" explains how stories, both concrete and hypothetical, are perfectly primed for such ethical experimentation: "Literature is a vast laboratory in which we experiment with estimations, evaluations, and judgments of approval and condemnation through which narrativity serves as a propaedeutic to ethics" (Ricœur, *Oneself as Another*, 115). Narratives, particularly those centered around the sociotechnical imaginary, create a stage in which technologies are centered as quasi-characters and ethical principles become normative considerations. In their simplest form, narratives are vehicles for imaginative variations concerning how technologies are deployed and received across diverse populations. The specific power of narratives to parcel such imagination into a digestible form informs Ricœur's argument of the narrative form as a propaedeutic to ethics since the hypothetical nuances of associating technologies with ethical principles are given a decidedly human face through mechanics such as plot and character. Additionally, the temporality of certain narratives to move beyond the present and explore future horizons impacted by the runaway development of specific technologies enhances the ability of narratives to envision consequences.

What is left in question with the use of literary genres such as science fiction to spur deliberations on potential ethical consequences of technological design is whether or not the literary imagination would conceivably be seriously considered as a productive means of articulating how a technology made for the "real world" should be designed. The history of science fiction and technological fictions as highly commercialized genres present in media such as pulp magazines (Ditum) allowed for these imaginations to be viewed as too lofty, primarily serving purposes of reader entertainment rather than providing social critique in any sort of serious way. Even today, commercialized science fiction narratives such as Black Mirror are often seen as too extreme of an imagination, something disturbing for audiences to watch for amusement rather than a meaningful text for informing how our

technology should be shaped (Ortberg). However, Ricœur's philosophy offers a counterpoint: "The imaginary variations in the literary field have for their horizon our unavoidable earthly condition" (Ricœur, *Time and Narrative*, 78). Put simply, narratives which discuss ethical implications of technologies or a technological society, even if they seem dystopian or outlandish, can reasonably predict ethical discussions of technology because even literature starts from a grounding of reality and observation of the world as it currently is. In this way, technological fiction becomes imagination with purpose; a means of spurring developers to entertain how even the smallest of design decisions could lead to large societal impacts.

Thorough integration of literary imagination into ethical deliberation is a beneficial practice precisely because taking imaginative variations as serious considerations means that developers would be pushed to envision consequences more holistically. As Ricœur argues, "The dream of technology... [and] the imaginative variations of science fiction deal with...the sameness...of one manipulable entity, the brain" (Ricœur, *Time and Narrative*, 79). Ricœur's specific invocation of the brain as malleable implicates that human thought processes can become flexible as they are exposed to greater volumes of imagination. The ideal technological developer would be one that could move outside of their own lived experience to imagine how the creation of a certain technology may impact or exclude those communities to which this certain developer does not belong. Thus, the consideration of science fiction and other literature as an informant for potential consequences of technology essentially allows practice for imagination in developers, encouraging thoughts that may seem outlandish based on their own lived experience but may well contribute to less unfair or unilateral design. In this way, singular technologies during the developmental process are able to be viewed from multiple angles, placed in societal contexts in which multiple impacts can be entertained.

It is important to note that in order for technological narratives to most effectively serve as a propaedeutic to ethical considerations, they ought to be more broadly defined than demarcations such as "science-fiction" or the literary imagination. Throughout this paper, I adopt the definition of "narrative" posited by the founders of the CEN project: "A historical (past and present), fictional, or real-world story/perspective involving technologies" (Bullock et al 1021). This definition encompasses not just narrative as imagination, but also narrative as past experiences of human beings whom new technologies are meant to serve. If narratives considered in an ethical deliberation include both fictions of technologies and concrete experiences of diverse groups of people, the design process has the potential to become not only more imaginative, but also more empathetic.

By nature of overlapping structural inequalities, those seated at the development table disproportionately represent the population of wealthier white males, situating other voices in an inherently disadvantaged position when it comes to having a say in specific design choices. Algorithmic Justice League founder Joy Buolamwini describes the "privileged ignorance" of "a largely homogenous group of people developing" tech products for diverse user bases not reflected in ethical discussions on design:

the very people making the systems are the people who oftentimes are least likely to suffer the harms. And so the perspectives in terms of what can go wrong aren't either being prioritized if they're known, right? They're dismissed, or sometimes, it's not even a question that's being asked... the ways in which we're even evaluating systems for how well they work doesn't include who I like to call the undersampled majority — women and people of color. You might have a false sense of progress because it works well for you and your buddy down the hall (Buolamwini and Swisher).

In cases where the "undersampled majorities" cannot be physically present at the developmental table to flag specific ethical consequences of design choices, case-study narratives can be helpful for illuminating how design choices for past technologies failed ethical principles of inclusion and ease of use for certain user bases. To reiterate, the ultimate amelioration to undersampling or excluding populations from the design process is a cultural shift to allow diverse voices to be physically present at the highest levels of the technology industry. But as such aspirations are not yet reflected in the structure of the industry, those narratives which successfully empathize with ethical failures of technology to serve oppressed populations must be particularly heeded for the time being. Buolamwini's voice has particular relevance to the failure of technologies catered to a market of white men to fairly impact women and people of color; her cutting-edge research spawned from an arresting experience in which a facial recognition algorithm failed to recognize her face as an actual face until she donned a white mask. These sorts of disparate impacts are exactly the failures disproportionately white male tech designers may be unable to consider without an attuned sense of empathy. Narratives, whether case-studies or loftier technological fictions, can aid in the cultivation of such empathy. From the perspective of fictional narratives to hone compassion for diverse population, a team of researchers including Emanuelle Burton, Judy Goldsmith, and Nicholas Mattei endorse that "science fiction creates an opportunity...to gain fresh insight into, and even empathy for, ethical positions and people whose real-world analogues are not embraced by their values or politics" (Burton et al 60). Considering such a diversity of voices and lived experiences of those usually marginalized or excluded from the full functionality

of technological artifacts proactively, before a technology is design, developed, and deployed, is crucial to improving the technological development process.

1.2 Imaginative Variations in A Priori Deliberations

Narratives, whether historical or fictional, can introduce a significant number of varying viewpoints into the deliberative process. The various perspectives on societal impacts of certain technologies or design choices afforded by a wealth of imaginative variations is particularly important at developmental tables. Even as it becomes easier and easier for a technology company to launch a piece of software into a given society, the composition of those who sit at any theoretical development table remains as unlikely as ever to fully represent the composition of the audience whose lives the product will impact. I aim to conceptualize how the inclusion of a greater number of narrative threads directly results in better informed ethical decisions in the technology development process. As narratives allow for a hermeneutic process of ethical decision making, I argue, an *a priori* approach to technological ethics considerations could become a new standard as a wealth of narrative threads hold the potential to bring a wealth of wisdom and perspective to a single developmental table. As the example of Timnit Gebru, which I develop later, demonstrates, the dismissal of voices directly pertinent to ensuring the ethical impacts of technologies is a current and prominent flaw of the technological design process that narratives have specific capability to address.

The importance of any approach, including the imaginative variations of fiction and use of real-world “case study” narratives, which introduces an inclusive range of voices into technological design considerations cannot be understated in an industry whose highest levels are notoriously exclusive and inaccessible. In her 2021 book on the notable absence of female voices in certain online forums such as comment sections, journalist Marie Tessier states that “the technology sector has been dominated by a particular type of engineer, entrepreneur, and venture capitalist—white guys—and they have as many implicit biases as anyone else” (Tessier 150). As Tessier is quick to point out, not all biases which find themselves baked into technology products are intentional; yet biased technologies are still an inevitable result when their designers encompass the worldview of a small population that does not represent the full user base of the product. As the constraints of racism, sexism, and other tangible forms of bias within the technology industry and society at a much broader scale allow the upper echelons of designer groups to consist disproportionately of white men, any means of introducing marginalized voices to those developmental tables becomes necessary, even if the ultimate solution lies in a broader cultural shift which facilitates the total inclusion of marginalized groups at these design tables. While a narrative approach to ethical consideration fulfills this role and fosters an empathy that ultimately plays a crucial role in a shift in industry culture, sensibility developed through narrative consideration is simply one factor involved in ultimately making ethical decisions and taking ethical action. As Ruha Benjamin argues in her book *Race After Technology*, “just having a more diverse team is an inadequate solution to discriminatory design practices that grow out of the interplay of racism and capitalism” (Benjamin 28). Ultimately, the lack of diverse perspectives present at the developmental table has deep roots that extend far beyond the technology industry itself. Thus, hasty development of biased or unethical technologies may still see benefit in the technology industry as its introduction into a racist, sexist society flies without consequence to the white men seated at the development table. Any cultural shift within the technology industry which allows for presence of marginalized groups at developmental tables must then also be accompanied by a narrative approach to ethical considerations which can envisage how populations of the larger society would be affected by a given technology product. Narratives as the gateway to a hermeneutic understanding of the constraints and hardships of broader society intertwines with the notion of conceptualizing the full, myriad range of positive and negative impacts of a technology product on many diverse populations before the product is released into the world, referred to here as an *a priori* approach. This crucial role of narratives to bear perspectives and potential impacts is pivotal to clarifying precisely why a greater plurality of narratives is the linchpin of a good ethical deliberation.

In Nascimento’s paper on the utility of narratives in constructing practical wisdom involving technology, he describes the consideration of multiple narratives in an ethical deliberation using a lexicon that calls to mind the imagery of a loom. In Nascimento’s model, the loom signifies “an ethical decision [which] takes place at a hypothetical moment in time at the end of a pronetical deliberation” (Nascimento 30). “Pre-deliberation narratives” which involve “actions, motives, values, incidents, facts, and interpretations considered by deliberators” constitute individual threads inserted into the loom, and together weave into “an encompassing narrative” known as a prospective narrative which can “take into account the multiplicity of ways in which technologies will affect others in diverse contexts” (Nascimento 30). Narratives add value to the deliberative process because if each thread represents a different point of view on how a technology is designed or used, a decision informed by many narratives

will ultimately be richer. Such narratives do not necessarily need to be science fiction either; any sort of voice or genre that applies to the decision on hand can serve as a pre-deliberation narrative. As with any sort of weaving job, the end goal is to ensure that the product is dense and sturdy rather than threadbare; in this instance, more imaginative threads in the ethical decision at hand aids with what Nascimento mentions as the “phronetic plurality.” Small groups of people who undertake increasingly complex tasks such as creating and deploying new technologies must need a deliberation which encompasses more than “the ability of only one person” or small group (Nascimento 33). A denser deliberative narrative, or a thicker product from the loom, has invariably taken a greater plurality of perspectives into its configuration, leaving fewer gaps created by missing viewpoints from specific populations. Indeed, Nascimento verifies that “by thinking and feeling through fictional and historical narratives, one is able to augment the threads and voices represented in the deliberative narrative” (Nascimento 31), once again emphasizing the importance of narrative representation through a balance of imaginative fictions and real-world case studies embodying former examples of technologies failing specific ethical principles such as inclusion. In the technological world, the group of people present at the development table will not always be representative of the entire sphere of users of a given technology. Through narrative threads, developers are able to build a better understanding of potential impacts of technologies on populations which may not be similar to them. When these initially disparate threads are weaved into a single prospective narrative through the process of ethical deliberation, the resulting developmental decision of a given technology product is more likely to pre-emptively prevent failures of a certain ethical principle as a direct result of this model’s focus on the baseline ethical condition of inclusion.

Ultimately, the weaving of a thick prospective narrative helps imagine “new action schemata that address the particularity of the situation, respecting others and deviating as little as possible from the ethical principles taken as its basis” (Nascimento 31). The use of narratives in ethical deliberation on technology and its impacts allows for a principles-first approach. The ethical decision focuses on a specific ethical principle, such as fairness or accessibility, that the technology would ideally meet. The pre-deliberative threads can then be used to imagine all the ways in which the specific technology at hand may fail those principles by bringing contextual possibilities into consideration. This helps developers take actions that would aim to prevent these ethical failures from occurring in the first place. Once again, a thicker prospective narrative is better because it means that the ethical principle has been thoroughly embraced and mediated through many different perspectives. In its purest form, this model of *a priori* ethical deliberation through an intrinsically plural prospective narrative returns to the mediation between developers’ focus on internal capabilities and external impacts; the foundation of ethical principles which emerges from the inclusion of as many imaginative variations as possible thoroughly externalizes what a technology will mean to its users, causing a shift from a focus on innovation’s sake.

Such externalization resulting from the inclusion of a large plurality of diverse views in impacts of specific design choices means that narratives are a crucial constituent of developing a model of *a priori* consideration of designing technology to meet pre-meditated ethical standards in large part because the prospective narrative ultimately embodies and envisions the integration of technology into human society. As stated previously in the description of the CEN project, computer science, especially in undergraduate fields, can tend to be viewed at a removal from the direct societal consequences of coding and ubiquitous computing. The use of narratives in an *a priori* ethical deliberation firmly places design or coding decisions in the context of societal impact through specifically imagining potential future impacts of a given technology. The book *AI Narratives*, which discusses the comprehensive history of technological fictions relating to artificial intelligence and automated/autonomous technologies, rectifies, “imaginative thinking about AI can probe both dystopian and utopian scenarios...anticipating consequences before they affect the lives of millions of people” (Cave et al 10-11). The specific power of technological fictions to present visions of futures in which technology plays an integral role in actively shaping societal structure means that the inclusion of such narrative threads into the prospective narrative inherently directs the ethical discussion toward future impacts of the technology developing at hand. In such a way, the practice of imagining the future in terms of technological enhancements is inextricably bound with an *a priori* approach because the setting of technological utopia or dystopia is encoded with the veritable notion that technology can have deterministic meaning in human society through changing the nature of the lives of its users. Making future projection a normative aspect of technological development helps center ethical principles based on this realization that technology can reinforce or challenge social norms with its affordances or limitations.

Narratives also move technology development processes closer to an *a priori* model of ethical deliberation through embodying voices exterior to those at the development table, making societal consequences more proximate. Critical to this consideration is Cave et. al’s proclamation of “narratives as constituent parts of any sociotechnical imaginary” (Cave et al 7). The

specific evocation of a “sociotechnical imaginary” not only implicates the inevitable marriage of technology and societal impact, but additionally serves the purpose of reminding that general public perception of technology and technological impact may be at a removal from how developers or coders perceive technology. Thus, because many narratives constitute the “imaginary” of the apparent societal impact of technology, considering a similar plurality of narrative threads when weaving a prospective narrative allows developers to become more in touch with how the common user receives and criticizes their creations. As narratives repeatedly assert the notion that any technologies developed will be both perceived and received critically by an audience of laypeople, they reinforce the practice of *a priori* ethical discussion because developers will aim to ward off those negative impacts which appear most saliently in the plural imaginary. Further, because narrative can be a useful vehicle for the voice of the layperson, some technological narratives may help developers consider “visions that are not collectively held, ones that destabilise institutions, and subaltern narratives” (Cave et al 7). Through the inclusion of voices external to the technology industry, or even any sort of background in computer science, narratives invite developers to imagine how products can better serve their actual diverse audience before their release, rather than putting the product out into the world and only seeing the consequences after the fact. Specifically, subaltern narratives in fictional and nonfictional forms can contribute to *a priori* ethical deliberation by bringing to light how oppressed populations have been specifically underserved through the lens of past technologies, which could inform the design of future technologies. As has been previously mentioned in this paper, the destabilization of institutions such as the technology industry is one step on a path to include marginalized populations in positions of power or impact more frequently, and pushing developers in the direction of progressive design through inclusion of minority conceptualizations of technology can lead to more concrete societal impact in this direction. As the argument of Joy Buolamwini indicates, it is unlikely that significant challenges to the structure of technological design or the technology industry will formulate internally, thus narratives remain as one vehicle for voices that can place external pressure on tech industry norms.

Because one goal of a narrative approach is to ground the discussion of the potential technology at hand in how it may meet or fail a specific ethical principle, a plurality of narratives which includes typically marginalized voices can be useful in defining the exact parameters of the ethical principle before designing the technology to specifically meet those parameters. The Burton et. al article points out that “any attempt to codify a universal definition of the ‘right’ way to be human cannot, by definition, take account of the particular social and ethical context of individual cultures” (Burton et al 56). This statement seems particularly relevant when considering the homogeneity of developmental tables mentioned by Buolamwini; the very definition of “ethical” impact of technology may be impacted or skewed by the fact that many of the developers may have more similar lived experiences to each other than to certain minority populations that may make up the user base of a given product. Narratives have the potential to acclimate developers to the needs of certain populations, leading to *a priori* discussion of how the technology at hand could meet, or at the least not impede, those needs. A multitude of narrative threads leads to an intrinsic plurality which leads away from one definition of a “right” design choice and into more nuanced territory in which disparate impacts on diverse communities can be considered ahead of time, rather than trying to adhere to one idea of what ethical principles are most important.

When searching for examples of narratives as a cornerstone for a model of *a priori* discussion of how specific technologies meet or fail certain ethical principles, the course “Science Fiction and Computer Ethics” taught at the University of Kentucky and the University of Illinois in Chicago, as described in the Burton et. al article, emerges as a similar action scheme to the one I propose. While this course focuses on how science fiction is a useful tool for fostering ethical sensibility within undergraduate computer science students, I believe the conceptualization of technological fictions as a crucial component of ethical discussion can be extrapolated to developmental tables of the technology industry, which is the focus of my paper. I invoke the course in this paper to emphasize the underlying *a priori* model of using narratives to launch discussions on how technological design choices align with pre-meditated ethical principles before the given technology is sold or otherwise released to an audience. The design of the course finds that “fiction offers students a way to engage with ethical questions that helps them cultivate their capacity for moral imagination” and “discussing ethics in the context of fiction can make it easier...to adopt an open-ended approach” (Burton et al 64), which is crucial to good ethical deliberation, especially in an *a priori* context. It is easy to see how narratives at the development table could be similarly effective in terms of making imagination more flexible and fostering open ended discussion on how a technology can meet specific ethical principles, and what populations might be affected by individual design choices. Also, narratives as a baseline of ethics, even if established in undergraduate contexts, sets a new norm among developer culture in imagining specific ethical implications of technologies. It is important to note that although this course focuses solely on science fiction narratives to spawn ethical deliberation, the mechanics of using the narrative form to bring consideration

of both future temporalities and marginalized voices into principles of technological design remain consistent as the backbone of the *a priori* model. My argument that real-life case-study and other historical or fictional narratives outside the realm of science fiction can prove to be valuable supplements to pure science fiction narratives is congruent with the model proposed by the course as an augmentation of the qualifications for a retrospective narrative thread to include in the prospective narrative. When considering developmental tables as the target of my specific recommendation for a narrative-based ethics propaedeutic, case-studies alongside science fiction become necessary as retrospective narrative threads in order to add tangibility and urgency to the potential consequences of a given technology, as the developers in this instance have significantly more power in terms of the societal impact they can proximately effectuate than do the undergraduate students in the course discussed.

As the successful pilots of the science fiction ethics course have demonstrated, narratives are intrinsic to a model of *a priori* ethical deliberation, indicating their potential to inspire developers to spend significant time considering how technologies can adhere to ethical principles before they are consumed by an audience. Setting this model as a standard in the technological industry has the potential to reverse the predominant yet ethically unsuccessful strategy of addressing ethical failures of technology only after their release. In *a priori* discussions of ethical technology deployment, the ultimate hope is that even one voice, one vision, one warning can be enough to impact how developers view the consequences of their creations. As computing becomes more ubiquitous, product development becomes faster, and deployment of new technologies affects more and more lives, addressing mistakes before they are made could prevent certain imperfect design choices from becoming irreversibly embedded in society, thus warding off dystopic realities like those presented in so many technological fictions.

1.3 Harbingers and Whistleblowers: The Pitfalls of an A Posteriori Approach to Computing Ethics

As the above section demonstrates, there are manifold benefits to an *a priori* approach to the deliberation of ethical principles met or failed by certain technologies, including the introduction of an intrinsic plurality of voices and the contextual application of ethical principles as an initial consideration of design. However, even removed from these clear benefits, an *a priori* approach is justified solely based on the fact that a *a posteriori* discussion of ethical failures of technologies has historically failed to make significant impact on how technologies are conceptualized or deployed unequally across populations. By nature, every digital artifact or architecture has stakeholders who will inherently hold more power or see more benefit than other stakeholders or users. Once disproportionate amounts of power consolidate around these stakeholders, which in the case of networked technologies usually tend to be corporations or advertising firms, any *a posteriori* discussion of how to tweak the technologies to better address ethical concerns is bound to be more complicated because the most powerful stakeholders will have a vested interest in maintaining the status quo of the given technology. Further, once certain design norms of specific technologies are thoroughly embedded into common societal use, such as the ability to interact with certain content in certain ways on network sites or the visual of like counts on Instagram, it becomes difficult to alter such design choices without fear of audience pushback. In this section, I illustrate historical failures of technological and network developers to successfully participate in *a priori* discussions of ethical creation. Through focusing on the marginalized or ignored voices of specific figures who either predicted or contradicted design choices of technologies, I demonstrate how emphasis on *a posteriori* as the only method of addressing ethical concerns sets suboptimal trends in which ulterior motives such as profit instead of ethical principles drive technological design.

The historical narrative of AI researcher Philip Agre exemplifies the consequences of a failure to use an *a priori* approach. As an “academic convert” from the field of computer science to humanities studies, Agre utilized his teachings in philosophy to formulate what have proven to be eerily prescient warnings about the nature of network technologies. In a pair of papers published in 1994 and 1997 respectively, Agre’s writing focused on potential impacts that eventually emerged in “Web 2.0,” or the umbrella term used to refer to the modern internet, in the age of “Web 1.0,” in which the internet was less interactive and user data was not as widely collected. His predictions and warnings were effectively narrativized in the latter paper, titled “Lessons Learned in Trying to Reform AI,” and it is worth questioning in a general sense if the viewpoints of a singular person or narrative thoroughly and critically considered in the technological design process can be enough to lead to concrete changes in the design that would significantly shift power from one stakeholder to another. This is especially important to consider in the context of individuals who, through personal experience or academic qualification or both, can offer a significant personal narrative on how technologies might fail certain groups of users. In the case of Philip Agre, his (at the time) unique blend of academic degrees in humanities and computer science fields qualifies him to consider the consequences of computer science decisions outside the isolated context of artifact affordance and instead allows movement toward critique of societal impact of technology. Reed Albergotti of The

Washington Post refers to Agre's view of Web 2.0 as "a startling vision of a future that has come to pass in the form of a data industrial complex that knows no borders and few laws. Data collected by disparate ad networks and mobile apps for myriad purposes is being used to sway elections or, in at least one case, to out a gay priest" (Albergotti). This reference to a future which has come to pass seems specifically intertwined with how technology inevitably becomes engrained into certain societal forces as opposed to existing in isolation. In the case of Agre's prediction, he foretold that the "data industrial complex" as an offshoot of capitalist economies to which network technology was introduced would allow those corporations which could transform personal data into a valuable commodity to have significant hegemony within digital spaces. Indeed, Agre specifically argued that through digital artifacts such as social networking sites which humans could use to interact with each other or with content, "the mass collection of data would change and simplify human behavior to make it easier to quantify" (Albergotti). The article corroborates Agre's prediction through directly drawing the aforementioned parallel: "social media and other online networks have corralled human interactions into easily quantifiable metrics, such as being friends or not, liking or not, a follower or someone who is followed.... data generated by those interactions further shape[s] behavior, by targeting messages meant to manipulate people psychologically" (Albergotti). As discussed in the previous sections, developers can easily ignore fictionalized predictions of technological dystopias through claiming that the distance of fiction from serious discourse on reality means that such visions would never come to pass. But the example of Philip Agre begs the question of how an expert's prescient opinion seemed to be entirely ignored in the conceptualization and development of Web 2.0.

The tale of Philip Agre's predictions decidedly shows that *a priori* ethical deliberations which incorporate voices external to design tables hold more realistic potential to address ethical concerns of how certain actors may manipulate digital artifacts or architectures than do *a posteriori* discussions of ethical issues that could be addressed. As Albergotti's article observes, "many of the ideas and conclusions that Agre explored in his academic research and his writing are only recently cropping up at think tanks and nonprofits focused on holding technology companies accountable" (Albergotti). The deliberations on the ethical failures of network technologies to prevent the massive aggregation of capital or mining of data by corporations which Albergotti references here as occurring on contemporary forums are thoroughly *a posteriori*; rather than the initial design of network technologies placing significant guardrails on the power of corporations, the solution to affording the average user greater agency over their data in network technologies is rather to regulate corporations through means such as legislation or accountability after power has already been apportioned to them. Thus, in *a posteriori* approaches to ethical dilemmas, it becomes apparent that other motives, such as profit or convenience, are weighed more heavily than the motive for design to be as ethical as possible. The eminent risk of deliberately leaving ethical concerns as a retroactive correction to existing technology rather than notions that are embedded into the design process from the start is that certain technologies might reach a point of such profound normalization or benefit for corporate stakeholders that their course cannot be significantly corrected.

Another notable tenet of Agre's philosophy which renders his personal narrative particularly applicable to technology developers involves his conceptualization of the computer science field of his time as isolated from other academic disciplines. As the Albergotti article describes, Agre and his colleagues "observed that computer scientists viewed their work in a vacuum largely disconnected from the world around it. At the same time, people outside that world lacked a deep enough understanding of technology or how it was about to change their lives" (Albergotti). Agre's observation accords with my earlier argument that even the contemporary computer science field can tend to view their work as affordance-based and inherently removed from the societal contexts that the developed technologies will eventually impact, hence the need for projects such as CEN. A narrative-based *a priori* approach to ethical deliberation, as opposed to *a posteriori* consideration of how to improve technologies, ultimately embeds recognition that any and all technologies hold potential to impact social contexts and human agency. Narrative thus become helpful for mediating the gap which Albergotti describes between computer-science-focused developers and the average users who may fail to understand unsimplified technologies. Through narrative, the perspectives of both humanities experts such as Agre and the laypeople who will experience digital artifacts can make their way to the development table, thus addressing Agre's concern of the "vacuum" in which the field of AI sees itself as above critique. Simultaneously, it ultimately falls upon developers to take narratives seriously as a means of fostering predictions of ethical failures or consequences of digital artifacts since, as Agre points out, responsibility cannot fall on laypeople or average users to foresee how specific digital artifacts will mold societal contexts. Overall, Agre's argument based on his experience in humanities fields after training in computer science that "criticism should be part of the process of building AI" (Albergotti) renders his historical narrative as self-reflexive support for a narrative approach to computing ethics based on the affordance of narratives to provide external criticism for computing experts.

Introducing this external criticism into the design process of technologies is crucial given that the emphasis on the profit motive for technology corporations has concretely foreclosed *a posteriori* discussions on how to improve the ethical sensibilities of network technologies. The personal narratives of Dr. Timnit Gebru and Frances Haugen illustrate the lack of concern which successful technology developers feel empowered to show toward external voices when their previous technologies have proven so lucrative. This returns to the question of power raised earlier; since the respective corporations of Google and Facebook have become primary stakeholders in network technologies who were able to use architectures to consolidate power and capital in their business models, it is more difficult to formulate an incentive for these corporations to willingly cede their power in the technology industry. Whereas *a priori* ethical deliberations leave room for other considerations aside from profit to be entertained at the developmental table, *a posteriori* ethical deliberations are usually trumped by the profitability of the current unethical state of the technologies. In the case of Dr. Gebru, who provided substantial research to Google explaining the unethical aspects of training natural language processing (NLP) algorithms on data from all over the internet, her voice and years of expertise in algorithmic bias were dismissed due to her criticism of Google's (profitable) data collection practices (Hao). Google punished Dr. Gebru's actions through pre-emptively firing her as their AI ethicist, despite the fact that she was initially hired to provide a new perspective on how technological innovations of Google failed certain ethical principles (Langley). Frances Haugen emerged as a whistleblower against Facebook for similar concerns revolving around an underlying AI system used in the corporation's main social media products; Haugen revealed that Facebook's algorithm drives engagement among young people by showing users progressively more extreme or divisive content, which included posts fostering negative social comparison and even posts glorifying or promoting eating disorders (McCluskey). In both cases, exterior voices pointing out the gaping design flaws of the technologies of these corporations do not hold much sway in causing concrete changes to the design simply because the corporations have built up enough power and profit to make the ethical impacts of their technologies a secondary concern. In the case of Dr. Gebru, Google was able to literally silence her voice because her suggestions for more ethical computing would interfere with their current business and data mining model.

Although both Dr. Gebru and Ms. Haugen valiantly led *a posteriori* discussions in how existing technologies could be altered to more effectively meet ethical principles, they ultimately fight somewhat of a losing battle because once a technology is shown to be successful in turning a profit, this intuitively becomes a primary basis from which to judge the artifact, while ethical considerations become secondary. The introduction of narratives into an *a priori* deliberation on how a given technological artifact could clear crucial ethical principles would create a new norm in which technology developers could move beyond thinking about digital artifacts in terms of profitability alone and instead more easily conceptualize potential impacts on diverse sects of the user base. For example, in the case of Frances Haugen's warnings, any narrative which posed questions such as "how can the design of a digital social platform avoid capitalizing on teenagers' insecurity and body dysmorphia to sell space to advertising companies and instead foster a space that does not innately force social comparison?" would have been a useful consideration prior to the creation of Facebook to provide the best hope for avoiding this current impact of the platform. In the case of Facebook, using narrative in a hypothetical *a priori* deliberation to ameliorate issues with the platform before its creation would have inevitably relied fairly heavily on prediction; since Facebook emerged as a unique social networking site at a time in which widespread social media platforms were limited, or at least not widely used, any imaginative variations in the pre-deliberation narratives would have needed some degree of predicting theoretical impacts without the benefit of too much tangible history. As discussed earlier in this paper, technological fictions, while not always seen as serious contributions to conversations on the real life impacts of technology, certainly comprise one realm which cultivates thriving predictions of how a technology could grow and embed itself into society, leading to inevitable consequences for users. This then raises the question of how effectively predictive technological fictions, even those that may seem outlandish, can launch *a priori* ethical discussions of how a specific technology will impact its diverse user base through considering how said technology is envisioned in the sociotechnical imaginary. I now shift focus to exploring this question through a close look at one such predictive technological fiction.

2 NARRATIVES OF PREDICTION: USING SCIENCE FICTION TO INFORM A PRIORI ETHICAL DELIBERATION

Having explained my reasoning behind the affordances of a narrative approach to launching *a priori* ethical discussions of how the design of technology should meet specific ethical principles, I now move to demonstrating this theory in practice through

a close reading of a science-fiction narrative. Through analyzing this short story through its representation of technology in terms of plot, character, and rhetoric, I aim to make a case for how careful attention to the embodiment of technology in narratives can result in fruitful ethical discussion of what similar technologies may mean in the real world.

In selecting which narratives to dissect in order to prove the capabilities of literary analysis to offer meaningful hypotheticals through which to consider how to ethically design technology, I focused upon a few principle criteria. Firstly, although the previous portions of the paper emphasized the importance of considering case-studies as crucial pre-deliberation narratives at design table, for the purpose of this paper, I choose to dissect literary fiction for the following reasons:

- Science-fiction literature, although usually a reflection or criticism of real society as it stands, often has rhetorical statements that are encoded in layers of literary meaning which can be decoded to align with specific messages or recommendations.
- Whereas “real world” case study narratives tend to be straightforward in terms of their lessons on negative ethical impacts of a given technology, any fictional pre-deliberation narratives may bring more of an ethical “gray area” through its hypothetical examples, which launches a more wholistic ethical discussion.
- As the example of Philip Agre in the previous section demonstrated, prediction is one cornerstone element of the prospective narrative since the goal of *a priori* deliberation is to imagine how technologies could fail ethical principles. Science fiction narratives offer a clear avenue to such imaginations, since the technologies they depict parallel, but do not exactly imitate, existing technologies. In this way, science fiction narratives hold potential to be both inherently predictive and to aim these predictions toward how specific design elements of technologies lead to their ethical failures.
- Because science fiction narratives often contain situations that at a glance can seem highly hypothetical, showing their pertinence to ethical discussions demonstrates how they can contribute to the practice of rendering more flexible the imagination of developers (as the Ricœur quote from earlier in this essay demonstrates).
- The hypotheticality of plotlines or technological impacts present in science fiction further introduces a requisite amount of distance between the current impact of technology and a potential future impact of technology, contributing to the *a priori* notion through representing avoidable crises.
- Finally, the specific lens of character in literary fiction allows developers to connect to the average person who uses or experiences a technology, ameliorating the removal which Agre described. Further, this use of character inherently rests on the fact that technology inevitably embeds itself in, and subsequently changes, societal contexts.

Secondly, I aimed to search for narratives which included technologies whose existence had no direct parallel to technologies that existed at the time these narratives were authored. The goal of this criterion was to find narratives which successfully predicted ethical discussions of technologies before those technologies appeared in the real world. Equally important to this criterion is that the hypothetical technologies introduced in the narrative were accompanied by some commentary, through plot or character, on what societal contexts would be impacted through their deployment.

Finally, I wished to find narratives which raised ethical discussions involving the design or deployment of specific technologies that could prove specifically relevant to current ethical discussions of technologies which either already exist or have been proposed. Through generalizing the ethical concerns raised through these fictional narratives, I hope to explore how such questions can be applied to the primary digital debates of the current era.

Given these criteria, I choose to analyze a short story which thoroughly explores the ethical and societal consequences of network technologies with fundamental design flaws. Through explaining the affordances of these technologies as well as their limitations and the imbalance between stakeholders, this story successfully proves its worth as a pre-deliberation narrative in considering how the design or implementation of technologies could be tweaked to more widely empower the user base. I delve into the world of William Gibson’s “Burning Chrome,” a story notorious for introducing the term “Cyberspace” to the digital cultural zeitgeist which explores the nature of hegemony, value exchange, and sense of place in network technologies. I will include discussion of how the ethical questions raised by this narrative remain pertinent to current ethical deliberations in the technology industry.

2.1 An Environment in its Own Right: *Burning Chrome*’s Vision of the Networked World

William Gibson, a renowned speculative fiction and science fiction author, had his short story “Burning Chrome” published in the science magazine *Omni* in 1982 (Andersen)—a couple of decades before the era of “Web 2.0,” defined as an age of interactive networking using computers and the architecture of the internet. Gibson’s concept of “cyberspace” (a term notably coined in this story) became the springboard from which he launched his first novel series, *Neuromancer*, set in the same universe as “Burning Chrome” (Packwood). In this section, I analyze Gibson’s predictions of the “cyberspace” of Web 2.0 through close attention to his short story, specifically explaining how his visions of corporate data collection and the digital network as an environment in its own right are bound with the ethical themes of digital inequality and tech monopolies.

“Burning Chrome” is told through the narrative perspective of Automatic Jack, a freelance hacker who lives and works with his friend Bobby Quine. Their friendship becomes unwittingly tense as Automatic Jack fosters an attraction to Bobby’s girlfriend Rikki. As Bobby aims to impress Rikki by becoming wealthier than he ever could in his lowly job in cybersecurity, he coerces Automatic Jack into joining him in a scheme to use Russian malware to rob the virtual vaults of Chrome, a notorious cyber-criminal and brothel owner. While this “activist” scheme is ultimately successful, stripping Chrome of large portions of her wealth and power in the destruction of her palace in the virtual world of cyberspace, both Automatic Jack and Bobby both lose Rikki, who leaves town after losing her secret job at one of Chrome’s brothels. Tore Rye Andersen, a professor of comparative literature at Aarhus University, criticizes the “stock plot” elements of this particular storyline: “With its story of former criminal elements who grudgingly pull off one last heist, the bones of the plot recall countless other thrillers...the story’s...impact does not reside...in the formulaic plot” (Andersen 122). However, from the perspective of the reader, the lack of complication or uniqueness present in the plot allows for greater focus on the predictive creativity of the worldbuilding. As the plot begins in *medias res* and continues to alternate between contextual information and the thrilling entry sequence in cyberspace, the reader’s attention is drawn more toward the exact descriptions of how exactly cyberspace is composed and navigated rather than the exact reasoning behind the scheme to rob Chrome. The use of tropes such as the love triangle between Jack, Rikki, and Bobby and the reluctant heist provides the reader a level of comfort and familiarity that helps orient them around the epochal novelty of the concept of a virtual network space that can be navigated as a unique sort of environment.

William Gibson explains that the idea to conceptualize digital networks in the terms of “cyberspace,” or the notion of a veritable environment, sprung from observing children playing arcade games: “these kids clearly believed in the space games projected. Everyone I know who works with computers seems to develop a belief that there’s some kind of actual space behind the screen, someplace you can’t see but you know is there” (Packwood). This sort of imagined space of the environment provided by network technologies is tangibly detailed throughout the entirety of “Burning Chrome.” The lexicon used to describe the general concept of cyberspace created by the digital networks in the story frequently involves the terms “matrix,” “grid,” and at one point “chessboard,” all of which embody meanings of spatial abstraction, representations of physical space that are not necessarily physical spaces themselves. The language of the story specifically keeps aspects of the exact appearance and composition of the virtual “environment” vague, frequently referring to much of the cyberspace as being comprised of “non-space” that seems to be “infinite.” Indeed, the exact nature of this “environment” is that it is malleable, an abstraction to help humans navigate complicated relationships between data. The digital network space becomes an “electronic” continuation of the human world, a “consensus-hallucination” that serves as “mankind’s extended...nervous system” (Gibson 197), ultimately boiling the network down into a sort of environment that serves as a singular abstraction to organize data in a way that is instinctual and digestible to the human mind. Andersen’s article indeed corroborates that “cyberspace is an abstraction,” yet, in my view, “the decidedly spatial aspect of this nonspace” (Andersen 134) allows Gibson’s story to more deeply explore how networks, when considered as an environment, ultimately result in questions of who holds the greatest share of hegemony in these environments.

In fact, the functionality of “cyberspace” as a network primarily utilized to store and exchange data and the power dynamics of stakeholders within this architecture are both described in terms of spatial dynamics in the descriptions of the story. Automatic Jack plainly describes that the cyberspace created by digital networks is meant to physically demonstrate “the relationships between data systems,” and thus the environment contains “stars” to represent “dense concentrations of information” (Gibson 196-197). Yet on the ground level, especially in the realm of “legitimate [corporate] programmers,” cyberspace occupants will “find themselves surrounded by bright geometries representing the corporate data,” which ultimately form “towers and fields” all across the “simulation matrix” (Gibson 196-197). The incorporation of data as a spatial component of cyberspace not only underscores the primary function of digital networks as a means of visualizing and exchanging this data, but further conceptualizes how this data can spread and aggregate itself across the seemingly boundless “environment.” Imagining that bits of data would be

analogous to building blocks in a theoretical cyberspace formed by information exchange through digital networks situates them as the constituent components of the network environment themselves, serving as a prediction of the defining feature of Web 2.0. Bruce Schneier, a lecturer at the Harvard Kennedy School, explains how the proliferation of data, especially personal data, defines the modern internet through a metaphor of feudalism: those largest “powers” on the internet who can provide the best tools for helping the average user navigate the complex entanglements of information in cyberspace (think, for example, of Google’s search engine easily directing users to those web pages which best match their query) are similar to the “lords” who provide these services (or spaces) for the price of the individual user’s data, which in turn keep these tools, and the algorithms behind them, churning for the convenience of the average user (Schneier). Gibson’s vision of data as environmental components of cyberspace provides a visual enabler for this operation; individual pieces of personal data, whether in the form of identity information, textual information, or statistics, is literally the foundation of the networked environment. Further, Gibson’s rendering of data as tangible units seems a prescient prediction of how network technologies, especially social media platforms, often turn more nebulous data, such as the likes, dislikes, and exact political views of an individual, into quantified bits of precise information through abstracting these processes into digital processes such as like buttons.

Having made such a prediction of the dynamics of the theoretical environment formed through network technologies, Gibson’s story proceeds to explain how the power of data to serve as the foundation of cyberspace could have significant ethical ramifications. As briefly mentioned, the spatial aspects of the digital environment of “Burning Chrome” become illustrative of uneven power dynamics between the different stakeholders of the architecture formed by the digital network. The primary stakeholders detailed in Gibson’s tale manifest in the dichotomy between the powerful corporations who control large amount of data in cyberspace and the individualistic hackers and “legitimate programmers” who, while not fully representative of “average users” of the modern internet, are depicted as holding severely less sway than the corporations. Returning to Gibson’s visual descriptions of the environment of cyberspace, Automatic Jack reveals that “high above” the aggregated “data and credit” and the aforementioned “dense concentrations of information,” which are both physical abstractions, “burn corporate galaxies” (Gibson 197). The positionality of corporations as the loftiest entity in the environment of cyberspace, evoked as galaxies in an image painting them as the largest encompassing entities in this specific universe, reflects the hegemony that they possess within this networked world. Further, the aforementioned image of “bright geometries representing the corporate data” which forms structures in cyberspace (Gibson 197) solidifies that corporations not only exist in a God’s-eye position where they can envisage all of the data below them, but additionally that the units of data which serve as building blocks in cyberspace are specifically made of data belonging to corporations that ultimately build their structures of power. Andersen corroborates this reading through his explanation that the “virtual space that represents the world’s cumulated data” exists “in a hyper-corporate society, where the relevance of nation states seems ever more distant, and where huge *zaibatsus* set the agenda...the companies in Gibson’s vision of the future seem to have fully replaced nations as political subjects” (Andersen 123). Andersen specifically invokes *zaibatsus*, referencing what Merriam-Webster refers to as the “several large capitalist enterprises that developed in Japan” in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, existing as “powerful financial and industrial conglomerate[s]” (Merriam-Webster, “*zaibatsu*”). In labelling the corporations of Gibson’s story as such *zaibatsus*, Andersen makes a fairly unequivocal statement of their dominance in the environment of cyberspace, referencing Gibson’s world in a parallel to the capitalist tyranny demonstrated during the Industrial Revolution. Ultimately, this raises the primary ethical concern of how to manage hegemony of large corporations in the environments created by digital networks. As Andersen interprets, the concrete hegemony of corporations in cyberspace through the aggregation of data seems to almost render them as governing bodies in their own right, almost creating a contrast to the “real world” where nation-states would purportedly set the rules. Indeed, in his article on the construction of cyberspace in Gibson’s fictions, Professor of English at Mississippi State University Daniel Punday writes that in Gibson’s *Neuromancer* novel series, “the hive image [to represent the same *zaibatsus* referenced in “Burning Chrome”] describes a corporation that has no gaps and whose control is complete” (Punday 206). In the views of both Andersen and Punday, Gibson’s fictions depict, and thus predict, the ethical conundrum of corporations gaining control of the cyberspace environment created by network technologies before such network technologies were in common usage. This unequal hegemonic power of these large conglomerates is built on a foundation of aggregated data, an abstract concept visualized by Gibson to explain the nature of the power imbalance.

The ability of corporations to be the empowered bodies with a great degree of control in cyberspace makes sense in the context of the affordance of digital networks to create architectures which disrupt boundaries of the physical world, ranging from connecting people from different buildings in the same town to connecting people across international borders. With this lens,

Andersen's argument that corporations would potentially replace nation-states in terms of control over the environment created by digital networks is imbued with another layer of meaning; in the creation of a new "space" that can transcend any singular locality, governing bodies of the physical world are bound to hold less sway, leaving those bodies who manage and maintain the architecture of the digital networked space itself to hold a larger amount of power. While the label of such companies as *zaibatsu*-adjacent could be debated, it is difficult to deny that corporations such as Google (with their search engine architecture which helps the average user navigate web pages) or Facebook (with their social media architectures which connect users across physical separations) hold a large share of hegemony in cyberspace through their internationally utilized tools which collect the data upon which their power and profit depend. The power of providing digital networked environments specifically meant to transcend physical places means that those companies which provide the best services for enabling easy navigation of online networks are able to, in effect, set the rules of interaction in cyberspace environments. During the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic beginning in the year 2020, "[b]y using many online channels, including Zoom, Moodle, Google Classroom, WhatsApp, and so on, educational institutions were pursuing the form of digitalization" (Saha et al 171). Even before a pandemic afflicted the globe, Punday observed in the year 2000 that "object oriented multi-user dungeons" (MOOs for short), referencing cyberspaces which individuals enter using the internet, were "beginning to be used for online conferencing, potentially alleviating the need for participants to travel across the country or overseas to participate in business or research meetings" (Punday 207). As both of these case studies illuminate, the ability of companies to provide architectures, and thus cyber-domains, which supplant phenomena or spaces typically seen in the physical world (classrooms and business meetings, respectively) creates environments in which they will inherently have a greater degree of control simply by nature of corralling individual users into these intuitive and helpful tools of connection. Indeed, the disproportionate power of certain companies in cyberspace through their creation of competitive artifacts to provide environments of connection from afar impacts the agency of physical institutions such as schools or businesses through providing a simple alternative to connecting "in-person". Thus, through providing "space" in a digital form, it is companies who make the greatest number of decisions concerning how individual users interact in cyberspace, even if physical governing bodies provide some structure as to how digital architectures are used and regulated.

The ability of corporations to both control and create cyberspace(s) begs the related ethical question of what sort of agency average users, or at the least non-corporate entities, have in navigating digital networks controlled by these higher powers. The main representative of non-corporate entities in Gibson's story are the renegade hackers Automatic Jack and Bobby. In expository narration, Automatic Jack reveals, "legitimate programmers never see the walls of ice they work behind, the walls of shadow that screen their operations from others" (Gibson 197). The use of the word "legitimate" is contrasted with the lexicon used to describe Bobby in particular, whose role as a hacker aiming to break into the virtual vault of Chrome lands him the descriptors of "burglar" and "cowboy" (Gibson 197). These titles implicate Bobby's lawlessness resulting from his ability to navigate cyberspace on his own terms rather than remaining in the corporate silos or boundaries in which "legitimate," or average, individual users operate, thus somewhat breaking the rules of corporate hegemony in cyberspace. The "walls of ice" become yet another physical representation of the abstract concept of corporations' power to direct user traffic in digital networks, and the demetaphorization of this symbol becomes a statement of how individual users travel through partitioned sections of the network negotiated by the powerful corporations, rather than floating above all the data at once as the powerful businesses are able to do in Gibson's vision of cyberspace.

A close literary analysis of Gibson's descriptions of the visual and functional aspects of the cyberspace environment reveals that this story poses fundamental ethical questions concerning the nature of disproportionate power between different stakeholders in digital networks, specifically through prescient observations which mirror the advantage of corporate powers over average individual users in the architectures of Web 2.0. In essence, the story labels the dynamic of corporations building lofty positions in cyberspace on a foundation of aggregated data while setting the delimitations within which average users must act as unethical practice. In the age of Web 2.0, as the feudalist metaphor of Schneier indicates, causing a shift in this consolidated power dynamic would be a decidedly *a posteriori* fix, an attempt to correct the unethical data mining practices that affect the agency of internet users yet simultaneously bring corporations to loftier heights of cyberspace. In returning to the frame of *a priori* ethical discussion versus *a posteriori* ethical discussion, this section ultimately begs the question of how the design of modern network technologies might have been impacted if the specific narrative of "Burning Chrome" had been a cornerstone consideration during the process of its conceptualization. If developers of Web 2.0 functionality had considered the dynamics at play in Gibson's tale, might they have pre-emptively placed more robust guardrails around corporations regarding what sort of data they could collect

and how they could collect it? Andersen's reading compares the companies of Gibson's imaginary to historical *zaibatsus*; if developers had reached a similar parallel, might they have set standards for how to break up those conglomerates who amass too much power or capital, the solution ultimately deployed against the *zaibatsus* in the mid-20th Century (Britannica)? Once again, such questions in the context of the functioning of Web 2.0 as it currently exists result in a *posteriori* ethical discussion. However, Web 2.0 is bound to be simply one stage in the evolution of digital networks; as future developments continue to change the nature of how various stakeholders experience cyberspace, the specific ethical questions entertained in "Burning Chrome" ought to remain at the forefront of the minds of those who hold the most power within the technology industry.

2.2 Into the Metaverse

Having thoroughly explored the ethical issues posited in William Gibson's short story "Burning Chrome," I now explain how such ethical dynamics concerning network technologies remain pertinent in the current age, as discussions of drawing the public into the "Metaverse," led by corporate giant Mark Zuckerberg, are starting to be entertained at the highest levels of the tech industry.

Conceptually, the Metaverse relies on a similar foundational principle to Gibson's vision of cyberspace: that digital networks lead to a sort of "consensus-hallucination" (Gibson 197) of their user base that ultimately forms a new trans-local environment in which different actors can interact. In line with this conceptualization, I rely primarily on the broad definition of "metaverse" posited in John Herrman and Kellen Browning's New York Times Article: "a fully realized digital world that exists beyond the analog one in which we live" that could exist as either "a new frontier where social norms and value systems can be written anew" or "virtual refuges" depending upon social context, formed by "a variety of virtual experiences, environments, and assets...[that] hint at what the internet will become next" (Herrman and Browning). As the article specifically references, this definition is built upon two fictional portrayals of metaverses that seem to follow similar principles of Gibson's cyberspace: the setting of the Metaverse in the 1992 Neal Stephenson novel "Snow Crash" and the OASIS of "Ready Player One" written by Ernest Cline. I adopt this definition because it allows for the clear application of the ethical questions raised in the analysis of "Burning Chrome" to the potential development of a metaverse: the evocation of "a...digital world beyond the analog one" provides a simple parallel to the setting of Gibson's story, and the reference to the next evolutionary stage of the internet beyond Web 2.0 casts the ethical issues raised in the story into a new light of future relevance.

In considering the primary ethical concern which Gibson's story raises of corporations becoming the most powerful entity in cyberspace, with disproportionate power to direct the agency of individual users through the collection of their data, my discussion of the Metaverse will focus upon the company of Facebook's recent endeavors into coining and creating a metaverse for the use of the masses. In his TechStuff podcast, literature scholar Jonathan Strickland summarizes Facebook's June 2021 announcement of their general vision of creating a metaverse, explaining that the corporation's goal is to employ a metaverse architecture owned and operated by Facebook that would combine aspects of augmented reality, virtual reality, digital social networking, and online shopping to form a cohesive cyberspace environment within which users would interact with content and with each other. Strickland observes that this notion of Facebook of turning digital networks into a veritable cyberspace environment with which users can more completely interface sprung from the company's acquisition of Oculus, a company which peddles virtual reality hardware, in 2014. Using Oculus headset technology, Facebook began development on Horizon Worlds and Horizon Workplace in 2019, where users harness the affordances of Oculus hardware to enter digital network environments for the purpose of collaborating with peers in a workplace setting or otherwise generally exploring user-generated worlds (Strickland). The primary limitation preventing Horizon Worlds from reaching a much larger user base is that the ability to interface with this formulated cyberspace environment is contingent upon the ability to purchase expensive Oculus hardware. As seen in "Burning Chrome," Facebook's beta phase of Horizon Worlds and their nebulous plan to conceptualize a metaverse share a common principle of expanding the abstraction of "environments" created by digital networks into veritable worlds in which users would travel in a spatial sense in a similar manner to traversing the physical environment, yet the affordance of network technologies to transcend locality would apply equally to this expanded abstract environment.

With this foundational connection between Gibson's work and Facebook's proposed metaverse established, I now explain how the specific ethical concerns raised in "Burning Chrome" ought to be considered in *a priori* discussions of developing such a metaverse. As iterated priorly, Gibson's physical descriptions of cyberspace embody the ethical issue of corporations using data to gain disproportionate power over the underlying architecture of cyberspace, leaving the average individual user with overall less

agency. Strickland shares the concern that Facebook would utilize its ownership of the metaverse environment to seal its hegemony in the cyberspace formed by the digital networks; he explains that their creation of the metaverse as a means of augmenting the experience of networks could be a gambit to make the internet synonymous with Facebook. In essence, entering “the internet” through this Facebook-controlled environment would mean that everything from internet searches to online shopping would first be filtered through Facebook, with users interfacing with this metaverse to enter a cyberspace with all the same practical functionality of Web 2.0 (Strickland). In such a scenario, Facebook’s model of aggregating user data would grow exponentially, as their control of the overarching architecture would allow even greater surveillance of user behavior within the networked environment. Strickland compares this idea of data “fueling” the foundation of the metaverse environment to the science fiction film *The Matrix*. In that film, which contains a quasi-metaverse in the form of an environment formed from computer code with which humans interface, human bodies are harvested as an energy source for the techno-dystopian, robot overrun physical world, while human minds wander around pacified within the cyberspace environment. Strickland believes that Facebook’s metaverse would operate under a similar, albeit less horrifying, principle: as user motion through the singular metaverse to different network aspects, from social networking to shopping, provides more data about their behavior and preferences (Strickland), the data mill which powers Facebook’s foundational profit continues to churn, in essence making human beings the power source of this technology. In such a conceptualization of the metaverse, it becomes easy to view Facebook in the same manner as the *zaiatus* invoked in Gibson’s tale, in which Facebook becomes the most powerful stakeholder in the metaverse architecture through aggregating data at the expense of privacy of individual users. Further, with Facebook’s hegemony over this cyberspace environment, they could easily partition these networks to direct user traffic in a way that benefits their data collection model in a similar principle to the walls of ice described in “Burning Chrome.” Thus, the ideal use of Gibson’s story in *a priori* discussions on metaverse development would be to raise considerations of how to place guardrails around Facebook in terms of what data it can collect in order to best adhere to the ethical principle of privacy for the individual user.

CONCLUSION

In his 2019 *New York Times* article, Whitson Gordon explains the concept of a “proprietary eponym,” or a phenomenon in which one certain brand name becomes so pervasive in its category that it comes to represent that category (examples include labelling all facial tissues as “Kleenex” or all bandages as “Band-Aids”) (Gordon). In terms of network technologies, a common proprietary eponym emerges when a curious individual is told to “Google something,” the product of Google’s search engine becoming a verb to represent the act of searching the digital network for a web page providing certain information. As the representation and navigation of the cyberspace of digital networks continues to evolve past the era of Web 2.0, how can new architectures such as Facebook’s metaverse be designed with empowerment of the average user in mind, rather than becoming yet another ubiquitous network technology that wears the proprietary eponym of Facebook (especially as they attempt to rebrand to Meta)? In this paper, I explained that narratives, ranging from real-world case studies to technological fictions, serve the crucial role of rendering flexible the imagination of technology developers, thus allowing them to envision the ethical consequences of specific design choices on a given user base. Inherently, the consideration of such narratives a development tables promotes *a priori* ethical discussion, or predicting ethical failures of technologies and addressing them within the design process before they occur, rather than the current tech industry norm of *a posteriori*, or after the fact, fixes in a half-baked attempt to address the ethical principles which narratives can successfully ideate. Through a close reading of William Gibson’s short story “Burning Chrome” and the personal narrative of Philip Agre, I explored the failure of total engagement in *a priori* ethical discussion in the development of Web 2.0. Had the imaginative variations of Philip Agre and “Burning Chrome” been considered as cornerstones of the design process, ethical conundrums such as disproportionate corporate hegemony and runaway data mining in digital network environments ideally may have been alleviated or avoided altogether. Yet because digital architectures as they stand allowed for the consolidation of power around corporations, *a posteriori* ethical discussions of how to renegotiate the power imbalance between corporations and the users beneath them simply may not hold enough potency. Philip Agre and William Gibson have indeed shown the door into a lost possible world; one in which the entertainment of an abundance of imagination allowed for a richer, more diverse consideration of how digital networks could meet ethical principles such as privacy and equality to be the most empowering to common users rather than becoming the birthplace of a data industrial complex that gives rise to monopolistic technology conglomerates. As common users are drawn into the Metaverse, riding along the wave of cyberspace’s evolution, we can envision

an opportunity to fuel *a priori* ethical discussion with narratives on how this cutting-edge environment can be simultaneously comfortable and empowering for users and limiting to overbearing hegemony of corporations—and this time, the opportunity cannot be wasted.

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